

Barcelona Supercomputing Center

Bioinfo4Women Programme Annual Report 2023

**Barcelona
Supercomputing
Center**
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

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01 INTRODUCTION

The Bioinfo4Women programme (B4W) stands as a non-profit initiative from the Life Sciences department at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), dedicated to promoting the research contributions and careers of women in computational biology. Rooted in our commitment to fostering excellence, B4W actively supports researchers by facilitating the exchange of knowledge and experiences through a spectrum of impactful activities, including seminars, conferences, training sessions, and mentorship programmes.

As we mark five years of dedicated efforts, including a strategic redefinition and organisational refinement, this year signifies a pivotal milestone for the B4W program. Our overarching objective has solidified, propelling us to sustain established activities while fostering new collaborations on a global scale. Throughout the year, B4W has spearheaded a series of initiatives, both internally within the BSC and externally, strengthening the foundational pillars of our program—networking, mentoring, and research. Notably, we would like to highlight five key activities from this year:

- **"Train the Trainer" Training Proposal:** Acknowledged and supported by the EU HORIZON project EOSC-Life, this project amplifies our commitment to skill development regarding the integration of sex and gender dimensions in life sciences research and has developed a handbook of interest to other institutions.
- **International Mentoring Programme for Young Scientists:** An impactful pilot program designed to nurture the next generation of women scientists, fostering growth and innovation.
- **Sip & Science Initiative:** A novel approach to networking, bringing together diverse voices over informal gatherings, creating an environment for knowledge exchange.
- **Severo Ochoa Institutional Project (BAIHA):** The goal of this project is to systematically address the detection of sex and gender bias in AI tools and healthcare applications.
- **ELIXIR leadership and diversity programme (collaboration with ELIXIR-DE):** An ELIXIR-wide effort led by ELIXIR-ES and ELIXIR-DE which stems from the B4W experience and seeks to promote a cultural change in the leadership of computational biology in Europe.

Further details on each initiative can be found in the comprehensive report. These endeavours have proven essential in achieving our objectives, positioning the Bioinfo4Women program prominently within the international biomedical research community, and promoting literacy towards the relevance of gender perspective in our field.

02 OBJECTIVES

General Objectives

Objective G1. Raise awareness of B4W activities and goals within the Life Sciences Department, and further engage with volunteers willing to contribute.

Throughout 2023, the Bioinfo4Women programme actively promoted its activities across different groups in the department. These efforts included the introduction of the programme to new volunteers, aiming to encourage their active participation. The key initiatives undertaken include:

Life Sciences Department PIs Retreat (February 2023)

- The programme presented strategies for integrating the sex and gender dimensions into research.
- Principal Investigators (PIs) engaged in hands-on activities, fostering practical insights.

Life Sciences Department Retreat (October 2023)

- The “Red / Green Flags” activity is a dynamic engagement designed to simulate fictional yet realistic scenarios encountered by Life Sciences' PhD students in their daily research endeavours, particularly in the detection of bad and best practices for incorporating sex and gender dimensions into research. The activity incorporates identifiable red and green flags that prompt participants to discern and analyse critical aspects within these scenarios. Originally conceived as an interactive session for the EOSC-Life course, we decided to replicate it due to the positive value added to the participants. This activity serves a dual purpose: to immerse participants in thought-provoking situations mirroring the challenges they may encounter during their research, and to cultivate their ability to discern positive (green flags) and potentially problematic (red flags) elements within these scenarios.

“Sip&Science” Activity (2023)

The Sip&Science (S&S) sessions represent a novel initiative designed to facilitate knowledge sharing among junior researchers within the Life Sciences Department. The event includes posters or flash talks, followed by a networking session complemented by coffee and pastries. The activity provides an excellent opportunity for researchers to share their work, practise public speaking, establish new connections and identify possible collaborations. Furthermore, these gatherings also serve as a platform to discuss the integration of a gender perspective in their work and personal experiences in collaboration with the B4W programme. The S&S sessions that were organised during 2023 were the following:

1. "Experiences from the Bioinfo4Women International Pilot Mentoring Programme for Young Scientists" 15/03/2023 - Presented by Olfat Khannous, Beatriz Urda and Maria Paola Ferri. 32 attendees.
2. "Unlocking the Full Potential of Personalized Medicine: Overcoming Sex and Gender Bias in Biological Data" (01/06/2023) - Presented by Victoria Ruiz-Sierra. 40+ attendees (Sip & Science - WHAW edition).
3. "Women's Health Awareness Quiz" (01/06/2023) - Presented by María Flores Rodero and Claire Furtick. 40+ attendees (Sip & Science - WHAW edition).
4. "Getting things done" (25/10/2023) - Presented by Victoria Ruiz-Sierra. 29 attendees.
5. "Decoding disinformation in 15 minutes - How easily are you tricked?" (29/11/2023) - Presented by María Flores Rodero. 25 attendees.

Image 1 - Sip & Science sessions' images: 1. Experiences from the Bioinfo4Women International Pilot Mentoring Programme for Young Scientists. 2. "Unlocking the Full Potential of Personalized Medicine: Overcoming Sex and Gender Bias in Biological Data". 3. "Women's Health Awareness Quiz". 4. "Getting things done".

Objective G2. Alignment with BSC's Severo Ochoa (SO) objectives.

B4W closely aligns its core objectives and strategies with the goals of the institutional Severo Ochoa Excellence (SO) programme and with the principles of Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) at the BSC. Specifically, B4W developed the SO strategy for attracting and retaining outstanding female scientists within the BSC, and it actively participates in the EDI commission. The B4W contributed to defining the BSC's comprehensive EDI plan and, together with other BSC departments, is monitoring its implementation to ensure compliance.

Objective G2.1. Identify talented women in science to establish contact and explore potential collaborations.

During 2023, our commitment to identifying and supporting talented women in bioinformatics and related fields remains firm. This commitment takes tangible form through B4W seminars, where distinguished female researchers are invited to showcase their scientific work. Complementing the seminar, we organise a comprehensive agenda of activities, fostering dialogues between the invited women researcher and the department's research groups. We also present the B4W programme to the speaker, creating opportunities to explore potential collaborations and exchanges. (See list of seminars in section 3).

Additionally, this year we have initiated collaboration with the "Women for Africa" Foundation¹ to engage in their "Science by Women" programme². This programme is dedicated to promoting African women's access to science and technology, supporting them in their research careers, making their achievements visible and promoting their leadership in the international scientific community. We are currently working on signing a collaboration agreement between the Foundation and the BSC, laying the groundwork for a meaningful collaboration set to start in 2024.

We also initiated a valuable partnership with Monica Cano Abadía, a senior scientist with expertise in Ethics in AI and a specialist in Gender, Equality and Diversity at the BBMRI. Together, we prepared a project proposal successfully funded via the internal training call at EOSC-Life. The project aimed at creating a training course for trainers focusing on integrating the sex and gender dimensions into research projects. (see G2.4 section)

Moreover, we strengthened our collaboration with Sabine Oertelt-Prigione, Professor (Strategic Chair) of Gender in Primary and Transmural Care at Radboud University Medical Center and Professor of Sex- and Gender-sensitive Medicine at Bielefeld University. B4W has collaborated with her in the context of the EOSC-Life project and several conferences.

¹ <https://mujeresporafrica.es/en/>

² <https://mujeresporafrica.es/en/proyectos/science-by-women/>

Lastly, Bioinfo4Women has embarked on an ambitious proposal for the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Staff Exchange (MSCA) 2023³ to create an interactive community as an extension of the Severo Ochoa Project, for which there are ongoing conversations with several relevant women scientists of international relevance. (see 2.3 section).

Objective G2.2. Explore potential synergies with the mentoring programme.

Drawing from the experience within B4W, the BSC (as the representative of ELIXIR-ES) started a collaboration with ELIXIR-DE to launch ELEAD, the “B4W - ELIXIR LEadership And Diversity mentoring programme”, which aims to empower women in the ELIXIR middle management to become mindful leaders and support them in their career growth. This is achieved with the following main lines of action:

1. Setting up a mentoring schema and pairing middle management mentees with senior mentors from ELIXIR and its extended network.
2. Offering professional training sessions, both remote and face-to-face, on transversal skills required to become a successful leader.
3. Setting up a peer mentoring schema amongst participants, guided by a professional coach.

ELEAD has been funded by ELIXIR for 24 months and kicked off in June 2023, although its preparation started at the beginning of the year. There are 12 participants in the pilot, plus the respective 12 mentors. Further information on the training programme (June-October 2023) can be found on the ELEAD website (<https://elixir-europe.org/internal-projects/commissioned-services/elead>).

The pilot is a collaborative effort within ELIXIR and expands to other nodes that provide advice that is essential to ensure that it responds to the needs of all countries. An initial feedback exercise is being run at the end of 2023 and will serve to fine-tune the pilot and design future editions. Informal feedback received so far has been very positive, and we have incorporated some changes to the initial plan, such as an extra supervision session of the coach for mentors in 2024.

In terms of dissemination, ELEAD was presented at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting in Dublin (5-8th June 2023) with a poster (<https://f1000research.com/posters/12-751>) and a dedicated workshop.

On the 24-25th of October the ELEAD (ELIXIR Leadership and Diversity mentoring programme) Training Session VI was held in Barcelona, Spain. The training included a one-day session on “Communication for Future Leaders” and another day on a “Toolbox for Inclusive Leaders”, both

³ <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/calls/msca-staff-exchanges-2023>

delivered by professional external trainers. A face to face peer-mentoring session took place on the evening of the first day.

Image 2 - ELEAD Face to Face Peer Mentoring session: Participants and trainers, 24th of October in Barcelona, Spain.

Objective G2.3. Identify women scientists within and outside the BSC as potential participants in the mobility programme.

During 2023 the B4W programme has expanded the list of women scientists that could potentially participate in the mobility programme (incoming and outgoing). Still, this activity has not been pushed forward due to the lack of internal procedures to implement the internships. It is expected that in 2024 the rules and regulations at the institutional level will be clearer and allow this activity to kick off.

Objective G2.4. Incorporate the sex and gender dimension into research: development of guidelines.

Bioinfo4Women received funding within the 3rd Training Open call in EOSC-Life⁴, titled “*How to Integrate the Sex and Gender Dimension in Life Sciences Research*” (10/1/2023 - 30/07/2023, involving BSC, BBMRI, INB/ELIXIR-ES and EATRIS). The initiative involved conducting a comprehensive course⁵ to train future trainers to broaden their technical knowledge and skills

⁴ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/services/open-call-training/>

⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/news/how-to-integrate-the-sex-and-gender-dimension-in-life-sciences-research/>

concerning sex and gender dimensions in life sciences research, and the slides were made available openly⁶. As part of the course, a handbook has been created as a deliverable and is currently undergoing copy editing (draft available online⁷). A success story was published on the EOSC-Life website⁸. The course focused on the following topics:

1. Sex and gender in Society: Aimed at deepening understanding and exploring diverse perspectives on the complexities of sex and gender. It encourages critical thinking about the terms and addresses issues related to gender and sexual inequity.
2. Sex and gender considerations in Life Sciences: Participants learn and identify how sex and gender are categorised and annotated in life sciences. The course emphasises understanding the ethical considerations related to their use. The relevant aspect is to raise awareness about categories and tools to identify and mitigate biases in biomedical data and models.
3. Teach transversal skills.

The Train-the-Trainer session, held on June 28-29th with a participation of 10 individuals from different biomedical research institutions, had notable impacts:

1. Integration into Events: Elements from the EOSC-Life course were incorporated into the BSC PhD symposium on October 6th and the Life Sciences retreat on October 19-20th.
2. Dissemination by Damjana Kastelic: Damjana Kastelic, one of the participants, successfully applied the insights gained from the course at PRBB-CRG. She conducted a similar course to provide researchers with the necessary tools to integrate sex and gender dimensions into their research projects.
3. Handbook Sharing with PRISMA: The handbook, developed during the course's content creation, has been shared with PRISMA's director of education. They plan to organise a training course based on its content internally.
4. Recognition by ELIXIR: The ELIXIR leadership was positively impressed by the handbook and expressed interest in implementing the training and activities in their internal efforts (such as ELEAD).
5. Inspiration for SIB Biohackathon: The course served as inspiration for the Swiss Bioinformatics Institute (SIB). They plan to organise a Biohackathon in June 2024 focused on sex and gender dimension topics.

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/8183682>

⁷ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1IqblB5E1PQEOk50k1i1biz2ujFUv_hEx/view

⁸ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/news/success-story-integrating-the-sex-and-gender-dimension-in-life-sciences-research/>

Image 3 - EOSC-Life Train the Trainer: 1. Trainers Monica Cano, Davide Cirillo and Atia Cortés. 2. Trainers, content creators and participants. 28th June 2023, Barcelona, Spain.

Objective G2.5. Consolidate the research into sex and gender biases in biomedicine and AI.

The Research working group has launched several mini-projects and activities, each of them involving small groups of people who showed interest in the topic. The progress of each of them is reviewed monthly with the rest of the group. The multidisciplinary nature of the groups is key for a broad perspective that complements the knowledge and enhances the overall consolidation of the research endeavours. Additionally, we consider that the BAHIA research project, supported by the Severo Ochoa programme, has strengthened and consolidated the research line.

1. The Bias in AI Healthcare Applications (BAIHA) Project: BAIHA is a 2-year project funded by the BSC SO program, it is dedicated to systematically addressing sex and gender bias detection in AI healthcare tools. The project will build a community to conduct benchmarking events to evaluate sex and gender bias in various AI tools, with a specific focus on large training datasets that can perpetuate existing biases. The project uses ELIXIR's OpenEBench (OEB) to perform the assessment and showcase the outcomes on a web page, providing a valuable resource for end-users to make informed decisions, and contributing to the systematic assessment and mitigation of biases in AI healthcare applications.
2. S&G Social Media Research: This project consists of a study on Twitter (now X) exploring the connection between abortion, miscarriage and depression, examining comments and dialogues on the topic by both men and women and analysing the differences. The results of this work have been submitted to the call for papers of the 16th ACM Web Science

Conference 2024 "Reflecting on the Web, AI, and Society" (<https://websci24.org/>). The publication outcome will be disclosed on January 31, 2024.

3. Google Scholar Scraper (bias in the visibility of women's scholarly production): The Google Scholar Scraper project focuses on bias analysis within Google Scholar and its article recommendation algorithm. In the context of this project, software was developed that will allow the creation of an unbiased repository of articles to be added to the B4W web. The software is available on GitHub⁹.
4. ELIXIR Germany Biohackathon project 2023: This project consists of a study of the European CORDIS Database to assess the relationship between the funding of scientific projects and the inclusion of the sex and gender dimension in the funded scientific production both in terms of research practice and research teams.

Objective G3. Participate in an international event. (ISMB/ECCB 2023).

B4W did not organise any specific activity at an international conference/event in 2023 and rather concentrated on disseminating the programme where possible and contributing to events from specific projects and consortia (PerMedCoE, ELIXIR).

At the ELIXIR annual All Hands Meeting (AHM), a comprehensive poster detailing the B4W structure and mission was presented. The poster included information about the B4W working groups, accompanied by relevant links for attendees keen on delving deeper into the programme's activities. This approach aimed to facilitate engagement, enabling interested individuals to follow up and access additional information regarding the initiative.

⁹ <https://github.com/MARIA2M/ScraperGoogleScholar>

Objectives Communication

Objective C1. Upgrade the Bioinfo4Women web page.

The old Bioinfo4Women website has been updated and the new version has been released to the public in September 2023 (<https://bioinfo4women.bsc.es/>). The information about the activities, events, and seminars that are organised or where B4W contributes is available in the different sections of the website.

Image 4 - Screenshot taken from the Bioinfo4Women webpage (<https://bioinfo4women.bsc.es/>).

Objective C2. Communicate success stories from B4W fellows and other women scientists from the LS Department.

This objective is pending, it was not possible to develop the content until the new site was operative.

Objective C3. Continue to organise activities such as the 11F Bioinfo Women's Day, rebranded as "BSC Life Science Open Day by B4W", the WHAW, B4W seminars, etc.

1. **The "BSC Life Science Open Day by B4W"** was celebrated in honour of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th February). This year we held the activity on the 15th of February. It was a successful event with 35 registrations and 27 attendees. After the event, we compiled feedback and statistics to understand how to organise and improve future editions of the 11F.
 - a. Registration: most (89%) at the master student stage, from 9 different institutions, 60% Women, 32% Men, 8% Non-binary/Queer.

- b. Participant's evaluation (18 people) was positive with an average of 88% (excellent).
- c. Participants responded they were very likely to recommend the event for future editions (score 98,89%).
- d. **At least three attendees from the LS Open Day by B4W are currently doing their master's thesis at BSC.** The BSC has consistently attracted talent via participants in this event who have been recruited to do their master's or PhD thesis, from all editions (2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022). This event was their first contact with the BSC.

Image 5 - BSC Life Science Open Day by B4W: All participants and organisers. 15th of February, Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

2. **The Women's Health Awareness Week (WHAW)** has been organised at BSC by B4W since 2022, in honour of the International Day of Action for Women's Health. This year it was held on the week of the 30th May to 2nd June. Activities organised by B4W in 2023 in this framework:
 - a. Informative pills - Three pills on Monday, Wednesday and Friday, disseminated via social media and featured at the BSC's building reception (big screen):
 - i. First on Marta Melé's lab publication¹⁰.
 - ii. Second on pharmacy toxicity¹¹.

¹⁰ <https://x.com/Bioinfo4women/status/1663085718577598464?s=20>

¹¹ <https://x.com/Bioinfo4women/status/1663814994528444417?s=20>

- iii. Third on Autism¹².
- b. Round table at BSC Auditorium on 31st May with Carme Borrell (Manager of the Agència de Salut Pública de Barcelona), Marga Nadal (Director of the Institut d'Investigació Biomèdica de Girona (IDIBGI)), Víctor Obach (Neurologist of the Headache Unit and Stroke Unit of the Unit of the Hospital Clinic of Barcelona), and Maite Solans (Researcher and co-ordinator of the Hypàtic Community of gender equality of AQUAS) as participants.

Image 6 - Women's Health Awareness Week (WHAW) Round Table: Speakers, Carme Borrell, Víctor Obach, Marga Nadal, Maite Solans. Moderator Alfonso Valencia. 31st of May, Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

Objective C4. Draft a manuscript about the B4W programme.

This objective could not be attained due to the volunteering nature of the programme and the activities that took place during 2023, especially the EOSC-Life project and the upgrade of the web page, which were not originally planned to pose such a workload. The programme is mature enough at this stage, and the draft of the manuscript will be prioritised in 2024.

¹² <https://x.com/Bioinfo4women/status/1664545837395976193?s=20>

Objectives Internationalisation

Objective I1. B4W Fellows: expand international collaboration through the SO mobility programme, specify short internships (in and out of the BSC) with at least 2 scientists.

During the year 2023, we could not initiate any fellowships nor the mobility programme since the BSC's SO mobility programme policies were still not clear. The necessary actions and discussions to ensure the fellowships and mobility programme occur in 2024 are in process. To achieve more independence as a programme and pursue this goal independently, B4W is developing a project proposal to apply for a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Staff Exchange.

Objective I2. Promotion of activities involving different institutions (e.g. invitation to the B4W seminars to exchange information and experiences).

During 2023, the B4W programme has promoted a series of activities in collaboration with other institutions of international relevance:

1. **BBMRI-ERIC.** We have collaborated with Mónica Cano Abadía in the project "How to Integrate the Sex and Gender Dimension in Life Sciences Research", funded by the EOSC-Life Training Open Call.
2. **CIBA Gender Data Lab.** Since March 2023, María José Rementería has been a member of the Advisory Board of the "CIBA Gender Data Lab". B4W has provided advice on the statistical analysis of sex and gender health data at the national level, from a social point of view, to influence local policies.
3. **ELIXIR.** We have actively collaborated with ELIXIR-DE and other national nodes to establish the ELEAD programme (which promotes leadership and diversity within ELIXIR).
4. **Women for Africa Foundation.** We have established contact to actively collaborate with the Women for Africa Foundation in the "Science by Women" programme and are pending the signature of the legal agreements.
5. **Women's Brain Project.** We are continuing our collaboration that started years ago. This year, we have collaborated on analysing the relationship between depression, miscarriage and abortion. We are also promoting the signature of legal agreements to formalise this collaboration at the institutional level.
6. **ACM-WE BCN.** We collaborated with ACM-WE on training activities for the PerMedCoE project. This included participating in the career path session at the Summer School in June 2023 and participating in the PRACE training "Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists".
7. **WiDS BCN.** We have presented part of the work developed by the research working group in the Poster Session of the Women in Data Science Barcelona Biomedicine (WiDS BCN)

conference organised by ISGlobal and PRBB on October 11th with a poster titled “Is biological sex adequately represented in biological databases worldwide?” (see full programme and poster abstracts [here](#)).

Objective 13. Incorporate learnings from B4W into the ELIXIR activities to promote diversity and leadership.

See section 2.2 on the ELIXIR ELEAD programme.

Objective 14. Join a European consortium applying to funding to work on the promotion of women’s research.

Bioinfo4Women is preparing an ambitious proposal for the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Staff Exchange (MSCA) 2023 call¹³. The objective is to establish a global, interactive, and multidisciplinary community collaborating on comprehensive assessments of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications in healthcare, specifically within neurobiology. The focus extends to both technical and ethical considerations, with a primary emphasis on detecting and mitigating sex and gender bias in health and AI—an area where B4W has long-standing expertise. The proposal prioritises active engagement from women's organisations in academia and beyond.

This initiative aims to formulate a systematic methodology, proposing extensions to existing guidelines, best practices, and policy recommendations for assessing AI. The community formed will not only contribute to developing the methodology but also develop comparative evaluations to assess diverse AI tools. Additionally, the community will organise training and dissemination activities on the topic.

The proposed technical project is an extension of the Severo Ochoa project within B4W’s research line. The SO project aims to systematically address the detection of sex and gender bias in healthcare and AI tools, using the ELIXIR OpenEBench (OEB) platform developed by the BSC life department as the benchmarking framework.

Beyond the project proposal itself, this effort is strengthening contacts with other institutions in Europe and beyond with a common interest in the incorporation of sex and gender dimensions in research, and overall promoting diversity in science. These allies are identified as potential future collaborators on other fronts and expand the B4W network and values.

¹³ <https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/calls/msca-staff-exchanges-2023>

Objectives Mentoring and Training

Objective T1. Finalise and evaluate the pilot mentoring programme (finalising May 2023) and decide on its potential continuation.

This year the pilot mentoring programme, addressed at junior researchers, concluded with great results and feedback:

- The pilot ran from June 2022 until May 2023, and involved 8 mentor-mentee pairs. A further mentor-mentee pair was included in November 2022. All mentors were women, there were 8 women and 1 man in the mentees' group.
- The pilot schema and initial results were disseminated at ECCB2022 and informally on several occasions, both to internal and external stakeholders.
- Informal feedback from mentees was gathered halfway through the pilot, with overall very positive comments. Trust and confidentiality between mentors and mentees, and with the organising committee, has been essential.
- Formal feedback was gathered from mentors and mentees at the end of the pilot:
 - Most (67%) mentors felt that they significantly or strongly contributed to their mentee's professional growth (score 3.7 out of 5), and all found personal satisfaction in their experience as mentors.
 - All mentees responded that the programme met or exceeded their expectations and that it helped them to develop greater self-awareness and broaden their horizons.

After the evaluation of the pilot, it was decided to launch a new edition of the programme with a duration of 18 months, addressed to junior researchers and technicians (men and women), starting in spring 2024.

Objective T2. Design a mentoring programme focused on the transition from postdoctoral researchers to PIs and study its implementation.

After the evaluation of the pilot in 2022-2023, a parallel mentoring programme addressed at women postdoctoral researchers wishing to transition to independent research positions outside the BSC is being designed, and initially interested participants have been contacted. The duration of the programme will be 12 months, and it will include the formation of a peer mentoring group, with dedicated supervision from an expert coach, thus replicating the successful schema that has been running for 4 years with women PIs of biomedical research institutions in Barcelona, and in which Marta Melé participates. The maximum number of participants will be 6, and it is expected to launch in the spring of 2024. Mentors will be selected in a conversation between the mentee,

the organising committee and the Director of the Department, who will provide guidance and make use of his extended network of contacts if needed.

Objective T3. Design training materials about the “integration of the sex and gender dimension in life sciences research” to train researchers, and deliver a pilot training for trainers using the developed materials.

See section 2.4 on the materials developed for the EOSC-Life project.

Objectives Research Line

Objective R1. Investigate and make available a curated resource on sex and gender biases in the biomedical sciences bibliographic repositories (e.g. Google Scholar).

The software for the Google Scholar Scraper project¹⁴ is a Python tool designed to predict the gender information of authors in scientific papers available on Google Scholar. This tool utilises scraping methods to extract metadata information from the papers and cross-references the DOIs and authors' names with the Crossref database. To perform the gender predictions, the software leverages APIs, namely Genderise¹⁵ and Nationalised¹⁶.

Objective R2. Develop a guideline for researchers, providing specific examples of how to implement sex and gender dimensions in research in the Life Sciences department.

See the EOSC-Life Train the Trainer project handbook “Integration of the sex and gender dimension in life sciences research” in section 2.4.

Objective R3. Dissemination of results (talks, draft publications, participation in events, etc.) on the research of sex and gender biases in health and AI.

Date	Event name	Type of event	B4W contribution	Participant(s)
09/02/2023	PATC Courses. Introduction to Big Data Analytics '23. Gender bias in big data	Training	<i>“Bias in Science - Sex and Gender Perspective in Big Data Analytics”</i>	Davide Cirillo
11/02/2023	FCRi y BIST	Talk	Mujeres #100tificas ¹⁷	Atia Cortés
28/02/2023	4YFN (Mobile World Conference)	Conference	<i>“Women in AI panel”</i> (organised by ESADE)	Atia Cortés
02/03/2023	Visit Women Business Angels	Event	Presentation of B4W	María José Rementería
07/03/2023	BioExcel, BSC and PerMedCoE (Collaboration of ACM-W,	Seminar	<i>“Women in Science session: From the Top Secret Rosies to Women in HPC”</i> ¹⁸	María José Rementería

¹⁴ <https://github.com/MARIA2M/ScraperGoogleScholar>

¹⁵ <https://genderize.io/>

¹⁶ <https://nationalize.io/>

¹⁷ <https://www.irbbarcelona.org/es/news/encuentro-de-100tificas-impulsando-la-educacion-para-cambiar-los-estereotipos-que-alejan-a-las>

¹⁸ <https://www.bsc.es/news/events/women-science-session-the-top-secret-rosies-women-hpc>

	Women in HPC, B4W and WiCS)			
15/03/2023	L'altra radio RNE4	Podcast	Monthly collaboration	Atia Cortés
27/03/2023	Bioinformatics Master at the ISCIII	Seminar	"Sex, gender and racial bias in technology and AI applied to biomedicine"	Davide Cirillo
07/04/2023	Generalitat Catalunya	Round Table	"Reptes del Futur i Impacte en el Benestar Subjectiu"	María José Rementeria
11/05/2023	ANSA	Interview	"Investigan evitar algoritmos que discriminan mujeres"	Davide Cirillo
17/05/2023	Health Revolution Congress	Conference	"AI models for stroke prevention using wearable data"	Davide Cirillo
23/05/2023	ISGlobal Data Science	Event	"Building Responsible AI: Causes, Consequences and Remedies of Algorithmic Bias"	Davide Cirillo
05/06/2023 to 08/06/2023	ELIXIR All Hands Meeting	Conference	Workshop and Posters	Alba Jene, Davide Cirillo, Laura Portell.
06/06/2023	Martes de vídeo - Screening of "My word"	Event	"Talk with Dones Visuals about Biases in AI, at Arts Santa Mònica"	Atia Cortés
07/07/2023	Observatori d'Ètica i Intel·ligència Artificial, Girona	Event	Workshop and roundtable on Feminisms and AI	Atia Cortés
30/06/2023	PerMedCoE	Summer school	Keynote lecture II: "Sex and gender bias in research" ¹⁹	Davide Cirillo
30/11/2023	IdiSBa. X Jornadas IdiSBa	Congress	"Sesgos por razón de Sexo y Género en Salud e IA" ²⁰	María José Rementeria
19/06/2023 and 20/06/2023	Taulí Health Artificial Intelligence Symposium (THAIS)	Round table	"Sesgos algorítmicos: ¿La perfección imperfecta?"	Davide Cirillo
10/07/2023	Barcelona International Youth Science Challenge (BIYSC) and BSC	Talk	"Machine learning for biomedical research"	Davide Cirillo
22/11/2023	18th Forum Risk Management	Talk	"L'intelligenza artificiale perpetua il gender gap"	Davide Cirillo
01/12/2023	GET Symposium of the Human Technopole	Talk	"Sex and gender bias in AI" ²¹	Davide Cirillo

¹⁹ <https://permedcoe.eu/training/permedcoe-summer-school-on-cell-level-simulations/>

²⁰ <https://www.idisba.es/es/Actualidad/Actividades/ID/2640/X-Jornadas-IdiSBa>

²¹ <https://youtu.be/OBaSRIf0wDU>

03 B4W SEMINARS

These seminars are streamed openly and disseminated via social networks, and the recordings are available in the BSC B4W - Bioinfo4Women Youtube Playlist²².

- **Virginia Dignum**, Professor at the Department of Computing Science at Umeå University. “SORS: *Responsible AI: what is it and why care?*” invited speaker (16 January 2023).
- **Ana Conesa**, Research Professor at the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC). “SORS: *Benchmarking of long-read transcriptomics methods; results and insights from the LRGASP project*” invited speaker (16 February 2023).
- **Sofia Trejo**, High-Performance Artificial Intelligence Recognised Researcher, Computer Sciences, BSC. “SORS: *When AI is not the solution: from principles to practice*” invited speaker (20 April 2023). <https://youtu.be/9KjZNoRUEbM>
- **Jazmín Aguado**, Biomechanics Group Senior PostDoc, CASE, BSC. “SORS: *Biomechanics full organ simulations with a sex-specific dimension*” invited speaker (5 May 2023).
- **Núria Queralt Rosinach**, Post-doc researcher in biomedical informatics at the Department of Human Genetics in the Leiden University Medical Center. “SORS/WomenInBSC: *Towards interpretable ML and explainable AI for biomedical discovery*” invited speaker (1 June 2023).
- **Laura Luebbert**, German-Catalan Biology PhD candidate at the California Institute of Technology (Caltech) in Pasadena, USA. “SORS/WomenInBSC: *Efficient and accurate detection of viral sequences in bulk and single-cell transcriptomics data*” invited speaker (21 September 2023).
- **Petia Radeva**, Professor at the Universitat de Barcelona (UB) and Head of the Consolidated Research Group “Artificial Intelligence and Biomedical Applications (AIBA)” at the UB. “SORS/Bioinfo4Women/Life Sessions: *Deep learning: fundamentals, challenges and health applications*” invited speaker (26 October 2023). <https://youtu.be/j6TfRtnPyZA>
- **Silvia Osuna**, ICREA research professor at the University of Girona (UdG). “SORS/WomenInBSC: *Development of new computational tools and approaches for computational enzyme design*” (9 November 2023). <https://youtu.be/NksCdYDV9NY>

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https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NksCdYDV9NY&list=PLbABsNMD2jhxBw0PZkeiM8b2cRSLqjOYs&ab_channel=BSCCNS

04 PEER-REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

- Ruiz-Serra, Victoria, Nataly Buslón, Olivier R. Philippe, Diego Saby, María Morales, Camila Pontes, Alejandro M. Andirkó, et al. 2023. “**Addressing Sex Bias in Biological Databases Worldwide.**” BioHackrXiv. February 1. Pre-print DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/n9dkg>
- Buslón N, Cortés A, Catuara-Solarz S, Cirillo D, Rementeria MJ. “**Raising awareness of sex and gender bias in artificial intelligence and health**”. **Front Glob Women's Health**. 2023 Sep 6;4:970312. PMID: 37746321; PMCID: PMC10512182. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389%2Ffgwh.2023.970312>
- Rementeria MJ, Prol G, Urda B, Núñez I, Cirillo D, Valencia A. “**Inteligencia artificial y bioética**”. Chapter: “**Inteligencia artificial y medicina personalizada**”. (ed. lit.), 2023, ISBN: 978-84-8468-988-1, pages 47-70. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/libro?codigo=942621>